

Title: Deep Learning

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INTRODUCTION:

Deep learning is the subset of the Machine Learning in Artificial Intelligence capable of understanding or learn the representation of data in multiple levels of abstraction. It has networks which are capable of learning in unsupervised manner from data that is unstructured or unlabeled.

AIM:

To make sense of data such as images, sound, and text through multiple layers of abstraction and make better decision based on given criterion through acquired knowledge.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Deep learning allows the computational models which are made up of many processing layers to learn the structure of the data with various levels of abstraction. These methods improved state-of-the-art in speech recognition, visual object recognition, object detection and many other domains such as drug discovery and genomics It discovers the intricate structure in large data set by using backpropagation algorithm to indicate how a machine should change the given weights as we call, an internal parameter that is used to determine the representation in each layer from representation in the previous layer. Deep learning has methods like Convolutional Neural Nets (CNN) and Recurrent Neural Nets (RNN), one has brought improvements in processing image, video, speech and audio data whereas latter has helped understand sequential data such as text and speech.

Before understanding the algorithms CNN and RNN we shall be looking at the most common form of machine learning, it may or may not be deep, is supervised learning. Let's imagine we want to classify images containing various types of objects like male, female and a pet, each has been labelled with its category. While in training, the algorithm is given with an image and it produces an output in form of vector of scores for each category and this process is repeated several times. Goal is to to have the highest score of all for desired category but this will not happen prior training phase. We then calculate an objective function which computes the error or distance between the output scores and the desired pattern scores. The machine then adjusts its internal parameter called as weights, to reduce the error which are real numbers that can be seen as 'knobs'. In general, deep learning model has hundreds to millions of these adjustable weights and hundreds to millions of labelled examples with which to train the machine. To properly adjust the weight vector the learning algorithm computes a gradient. The weight vector is then adjusted in the opposite direction to the gradient vector.

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN): Convolutional Nets are designed to process data that come in the form of multiple arrays. There are four key ideas behind Convolutional Nets that

take advantage of the properties of natural signals: local connections, shared weights, pooling and the use of many layers. The architecture of a CNN is structured as series of stages. The initial few stages consist of two types of layers: convolutional layers and pooling layers. Units in Convolutional layer are organized in feature maps in which each unit is connected to local patches in the feature maps of previous layer through a set of weights called as filter bank. As the weight matrix behaves like a filter in an image extracting particular information from the original color, while another one might just blur unwanted noise.

Another main concept here is pooling layer where its sole purpose is to minimize or reduce the spatial size of the image. It is done periodically between subsequent convolution layer.

Lastly, there is an output layer after multiple convolution and padding. To generate the final output, we need to apply a fully connected layer to create equal number of classes as desired as an output. Convolution layer creates 3D activation maps while we just need the output as yes or no question to answer whether an image belongs to specific category or not.

Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN):

RNNs process an input sequence one element at a time, maintaining in their hidden units a 'state vector' that implicitly contains information about the history of all the past elements of the sequence. Generally used to predict a next character in the word or next word in the sentence.

Because of the backpropagated gradient either grow or shrink at each given step this process has issues of either vanishing or exploding gradients.

CONCLUSIONS:

Machine translation and other forms of language processing have also become far more convincing, with people unveiling new deep learning tricks every month.

KEYWORDS:

Deep Learning, Image processing, RNN, CNN, Abstraction.

BIOGRAPHY:

Sanket Ganatra has completed his Post-Graduation certificate in Business Intelligence from Algonquin College and Post-Graduation certificate in Big Data Analytics from Georgian College at the age of 26 years. He is Data Science Consultant at Lixar Inc., since September 2017. He was a part of Hortonworks Data Platform and Teradata in India before he started pursuing Post Graduation.